

Syntheses and Biological Activity of Heterocycles derived from 3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylate

RAJENDRA N. MAHAJAN, FREDDY H. HAVALDAR
and

PETER S. FERNANDES*

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory,
Department of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College,
Bombay-400 001

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ALTHOUGH many pyrazoles have biological activity¹, those which have found practical applications owe their activity more to the substituents rather than to the inherent activity of the pyrazole ring itself. In view of this and our continued interest in the synthesis of pyrazole heterocycles, we thought it worthwhile to synthesise pyrazoles and 5-substituted pyrazoles having 1,3,4-triazole, 1,3,4-thiadiazole and 1,3,4-oxadiazole moieties, with the objective of screening them for their biological activity.

3-Hydroxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylic acid² (1) on reaction with dimethyl sulphate in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate as deacidant resulted in the formation of 3-methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylate (2), which with hydrazine hydrate gave the corresponding acid hydrazide (3).

Compound 3 with potassium thiocyanate and a few substituted aryl isothiocyanates yielded the corresponding thiosemicarbazides (4a-e), which in turn were converted to the corresponding pyrazolo-5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (5a-e), 1,3,4-triazoles (6a-e) and 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (7a-e) respectively (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and the ¹H nmr spectra on a Bruker Spectrospin (90 MHz) instrument. Tlc plates (Merck; silica gel G, 0.25 mm) were developed in chloroform-ethanol (9:1). All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

- (1) R = CO₂H, R' = OH
(2) R = CO₂Me, R' = OMe
(3) R = CONHNH₂, R' = OMe
(4) R = CONHNHC(S)NHR'', R' = OMe

- 4-7a; R'' = H, b; R'' = C₆H₅, c; R'' = 4-OCH₃.C₆H₄,
d; R'' = 4-CH₃.C₆H₄, e; R'' = 4-Cl.C₆H₄.

Scheme 1

3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylate (2): To the acid (1) (0.045 mol) in dry acetone (100 ml) containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g), was added dimethyl sulphate (0.1 mol) with stirring. This mixture was then refluxed for about 12 h, filtered and the excess acetone removed under reduced pressure. The viscous liquid on trituration with ice-cold water yielded the desired product (2) which was filtered and crystallised from methanol (65%), m.p. 69°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 720 (C=O), 1 620 (C=C) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylic acid hydrazide (3): To the ester (2; 0.02 mol) in methanol (20 ml), was added 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.04 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for about 18 h. The excess of methanol was then distilled under reduced pressure and the mixture poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from hot water, (50%), m.p. 130°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 300-3 100 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 610 (C=C) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 3.7 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.1 (1H, s, =CH), 7.4 (5H, m, ArH) and 7.7 (1H, s, NH).

3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxylic acid, 2-[(substituted-amino)thioxomethyl]hydrazide (4a-e): A mixture of 3 (0.003 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and potassium thiocyanate (0.0035 mol) with a trace of HCl, was refluxed for about 3 h. The excess solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with cold water. The resulting solid

was filtered and crystallised from methanol: **4a** (74%), m.p. 203°; **4b** (93%), m.p. 176°; **4c** (86%), m.p. 151°; **4d** (89%), m.p. 182°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 200–3 150 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 290 cm^{-1} (C=S); **4e** (80%), m.p. 193°.

5-(3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)-N-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amines (5a–e): The appropriate compound **4a–e** (0.001 mol) was added in small portions to concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 ml) at 0° with stirring and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol: **5a** (45%), m.p. 101°; **5b** (40%), m.p. 198°; **5c** (36%), m.p. 216°; **5d** (48%), m.p. 203°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 269 (NH), 1 622 (C=C) and 1 544 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.6 (1H, s, =CH), 7.2–7.7 (9H, m, ArH) and 8.4 (1H, s, NH); **5e** (40%), m.p. 184°.

5-(3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)-1-substituted-1,3,4-triazol-2-thiols (6a–e): The appropriate compound **4a–e** (0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2N NaOH (20 ml) for about 3 h. The solution was then cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol: **6a** (60%), m.p. 232°; **6b** (76%), m.p. 211°; **6c** (83%), m.p. 184°; **6d** (81%), m.p. 202°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 2 500 (SH), 1 540 (C=N) and 1 300 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.9 (1H, s, SH), 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH) and 6.7–7.4 (9H, m, ArH); **6e** (75%), m.p. 238°.

5-(3-Methoxy-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)-N-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amines (7a–e): The respective thiosemicarbazide **4a–e** (0.001 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to 4N NaOH (5 ml). To it 10% I_2 in KI was added dropwise with stirring until the colour of iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 h. The solvent was then distilled under reduced pressure and the mixture poured into crushed ice. The resulting solution was filtered and the residue treated with 1N sodium thiosulphate till colourless. The product was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol: **7a** (37%), m.p. 265°; **7b** (45%), m.p. 248°; **7c** (45%), m.p. 224°; **7d** (40%), m.p. 216°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 300 (NH), 1 660 (C=C), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 060 cm^{-1} (C–O–C); **7e** (36%), m.p. 239°.

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for biological activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhosa* using concentrations of 2 and 5 mg ml^{-1} by the ditch-plate technique³. The following compounds were found active at concentration level of 5 mg ml^{-1} : **5e** and **7e** against *B. subtilis*, **4c** and **7c** against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*, **5a** against all organisms used except *B. subtilis*, **4a**, **6c**, **7a** and **7e** against *E. coli*, **6a** against all organisms used except *E. coli*, **4d**, **5c** and **6d** against *S. typhosa*.

References

1. G. CORSI, C. GERMANI, G. PALAZZO, B. SILVESTRINI and P. S. BARCELLONA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1976, 19, 778; N. N. DURHAM, R. W. CHESTNUT, M. M. HASBEM and K. D. BERLIN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1976, 19, 229; R. A. BROWN and K. A. RAMALINGAM, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 664; L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", Macmillan, New York, 1980; H. V. SRCOR and J. F. DE BORDELAHEN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 951.
2. Y. MAKI, H. KIZU and K. OBATA, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1963, 83, 725 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 1742).
3. L. J. BRADSHAW, "Laboratory Microbiology", Saunders, Philadelphia, 1979.